

Evaluation of Endolichenic Fungi as Antibacterial Agents: Screening for Antibiotic Potential

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Lichens represent a unique symbiotic relationship between fungi (mycobionts) and photobiont partners like algae or cyanobacteria. In addition to lichenized fungi, a distinct group called endolichenic fungi (ELF) coexist within lichen thalli without causing harm. ELF has gained recognition as a source of diverse metabolites, spanning alkaloids, quinones, furanones, pyrones, benzopyranoids, xanthenes, terpenes, steroids, peptides, and acyclic compounds, offering potential alternatives for bioactive substances. These compounds exhibit a wide range of biological activities, including anticancer, antiviral, antibacterial, antifungal, and anti-Alzheimer's effects. Notably, ELF-derived quinones, heterocyclics, and phenolic compounds demonstrate strong cytotoxic and antimicrobial properties, with phenolics also exhibiting antioxidant effects. Our research focuses on exploring the ELF niche within the Nagaon region for valuable bioactive compounds beneficial for human and plant health. Specifically, we aim to investigate the antibacterial activity of collected ELF and their extracts against various microorganisms, including gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. Through standardized collection, identification, and isolation techniques, we intend to analyze the antagonistic and antibacterial properties of ELF using solvent extracts derived from natural thalli on test organisms.

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